

ICT PARKS AND DIGITAL LITERACY IN NIGERIA

Eleberi Ebele Leticia

Department of Computer Science

Ebyfav2001@yahoo.com

Abstract

This paper investigates on ICT parks and digital literacy in Nigeria. The paper disaggregated information communication technology into Wifi, Mobile phone and social media as explanatory variables while digital literacy remains the dependent variable. Data were generated via Primary source through the use of a structured questionnaire and analysed through analysis of variance. The study found that WiFi, Mobile phone and social media has significant effect on digital literacy, it was observed that government should enhance the range of coverage of WiFi, since WiFi security protocols prevent unauthorized access or damage to computers using wireless networks

Keywords Information Communication Technology, WiFi, Digital literacy,

1.1 Introduction

The importance of ICT in our present world cannot be overemphasized and Education being the backbone of any nation is not left out at all level, this implies that education that is innovative and resource-based produces graduates who will lead the nation forward. To achieve this, there must be a move from conventional methods of teaching, learning, and research to current methods, which requires the use of ICT as a new technology that presents potential for enhanced personnel development. College lecturers are the foundational personnel of educational institutions, and they make significant contributions to the achievement of institutional goals. With the rise of ICT, college instructors now have a plethora of possibilities for teaching and learning.

Any form of learning that recognizes ICT is a crucial is as a method of educating college undergraduate students for the knowledge economy in the twenty-first century, since learners are now exposed to varied technologies and are now referred to be "digital natives" (Kumari & D'Souza, 2016). It is no secret that ICT has taken over modern life, and there is general acceptance of the necessity to employ ICT in higher education institutions as we enter the era of globalization, when the free flow of information via satellite and the internet holds sway in global knowledge distribution.

The use of technology in teaching and learning is quickly becoming one of the most significant and highly debated problems in modern educational policy (Thierer, 2000). Most education professionals agreed that, when utilized appropriately, ICT has significant promise for improving teaching and learning as well as influencing job possibilities. Kolawale (2008)

describes ICT as "technology that assist us in recording, storing, processing, retrieving, transferring, and disseminating recorded information."

This means that the user and the data are interacting. As a result, information and communication technology is a broad phrase that encompasses any communication device used for teaching and learning. This type of gadget could be

Computer system, communication device, telecommunication, phone, satellites, telex, facsimile, internet, email, fax, video text and document delivery, electronic copiers, radio, television, and so on. According to Olakule (2014), these networks connect schools, families, businesses, students, and hospitals, facilitating teaching and learning.

Previous academics characterized digital literacy as a collection of complex and linked subdisciplines that include skill, knowledge, ethics, and creative outputs in the digital network environment (Calvani, Cartelli, Fini& Ranieri, 2008; Covello, 2010). Thus, digital literacy entails more than merely incorporating technology into the classroom; it entails using technology to comprehend and create modern communication, to situate oneself in the digital realm, and to manage knowledge and experience in the information age for the benefit of students. As a result, the purpose of this research tends to investigate the ICT parks on digital literacy in Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of problems

ICT has been a transformational instrument in the educational sector, transforming classroom instruction to virtual learning in developed countries as a result of the ICT and digital literacy abilities carried by university and college of education teachers. However, in developing nations such as Nigeria, the application of ICT to the teaching and learning process is still in its infancy, with college of education lecturers having little or no digital literacy capability (Ebele, Ejedafiru, & Oghenetega, 2013). This is having a negative impact on the entire educational growth of university students, as university education is the pinnacle of educational levels in developing a literate individual, who would then change society into a literate society. As a result, the purpose of this research is to investigate on the effective use of ICT parkson digital literacy in Nigeria.

1.3 Objective of the study

The main objective of this paper is to investigate on ICT parks and digital literacy in Nigeria; the study will specifically achieve the following;

1. ascertain the importance of Wi-fi on digital literacy in Nigeria
2. determine the effect of mobile phone on digital literacy in Nigeria
3. examine the effect of social media on digital literacy in Nigeria

1.4 Research questions

This paper is guided by the following research questions;

1. what is the importance of Wi-Fi on digital literacy in Nigeria?
2. what effect has mobile phone on digital literacy in Nigeria?
3. to what extent has social media affected digital literacy in Nigeria?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: Wi-Fi has no significant effect on digital literacy in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Mobile phone has no significant effect on digital literacy in Nigeria.

H₀₃: Social media has no significant effect on digital literacy in Nigeria.

1.6 Scope of the study

The content scope of this study is to investigate on ICT parks and digital literacy: the Nigeria experience. The research adopts Imo state as the study area where questionnaires constructed will be distributed to customers of banks and telecommunication on their literate usage level of Wifi, mobile phone and social media.

2.0 Review of related literature

2.1 concept of social media

According to Jimmie (2014) Social media is the term often used to refer to new forms of media that involve interactive participation. Often the development of media is divided into two different ages, the broadcast age and the interactive age. In the broadcast age, media were almost exclusively centralized where one entity such as a radio or television station,

newspaper company, or a movie production studio distributed messages to many people. Feedback to media outlets was often indirect, delayed, and impersonal. Mediated communication between individuals typically happened on a much smaller level, usually via personal letters, telephone calls, or sometimes on a slightly larger scale through means such as photocopied family newsletters. With the rise of digital and mobile technologies, interaction on a large scale became easier for individuals than ever before; and as such, a new media age was born where interactivity was placed at the center of new media functions. One individual could now speak to many, and instant feedback was a possibility. Where citizens and consumers used to have limited and somewhat muted voices, now they could share their opinions with many. The low cost and accessibility of new technology also allowed more options for media consumption than ever before – and so instead of only a few news outlets, individuals now have the ability to seek information from several sources and to dialogue with others via message forums about the information posted. At the core of this ongoing revolution is social media. The characteristics, common forms, and common functions of social media are explored here.

All social media involve some sort of digital platform, whether that be mobile or stationary. Not everything that is digital, however, is necessarily social media. Two common characteristics help to define social media. First, social media allow some form of participation. Social media are never completely passive, even if sometimes social networking sites such as Facebook may allow passive viewing of what others are posting. Usually, at bare minimum, a profile must be created that allows for the beginning of the potential for interaction. That quality in and of itself sets social media apart from traditional media where personal profiles are not the norm. Second, and in line with their participatory nature, social media involve interaction. This interaction can be with established friends, family, or acquaintances or with new people who share common interests or even a common acquaintance circle. Although many social media were or are initially treated or referred to as novel, as they continue to be integrated into personal and professional lives they become less noticed and more expected Jimmie (2014).

Forms As this overview of common forms of social media demonstrates, some are used primarily for recreation or personal connections, others for work or professional reasons, but most allow leeway for both.

Email. Probably the most common form of social media used in everyday life, email (short for electronic mail) involves users logging into an account in order to send and receive messages to other users. Anyone who sends or receives an email must have an account. Many options for free email accounts are available via the World Wide Web, but many times internet service providers will also offer free email accounts with service packages or employers will offer email addresses to their employees. Most workplaces have strict rules about how email accounts can be used, although many organizations report that they have no specific email training. Those who work for public organizations (including politicians, professors at state universities, and administrators and assistants for government offices) are often subject to open records laws that will allow interested people or organizations to request any emails sent or received to a government funded email account or an email account used to conduct government business.

Texters. Similar to email, a texter is a two-way communication channel that allows individuals to quickly send a message to another person or a group of people. Although media portrayals often make it look as if texting is a particularly youthful behavior, people of all ages have adapted to texting. Still, younger individuals tend to text more often and usually do so at a faster speed. As texting technology has improved, it is easier to text photos or to copy and paste links into texters in order to share them with others. Texters often make use of emoticons, the use of keyboard characters to make pictures such as a smiley face (e.g., :-P), a practice that is also common with email. Texters are derived from chatters, or computer programs that make use of the internet to allow people to quickly talk back and forth via text characters. Although the use of texting is often highly convenient and allows many benefits, particular attention has been paid to two texting behaviors that has led to problems: texting while driving and sexting. It is estimated that texting while driving makes a car crash almost 23% more likely. Sexting is mostly harmful when adolescent children share pictures that are later redistributed to others by the receiver. In some cases, those forwarding pictures of people under the age of 18 have been charged with child pornography. Politicians have faced scrutiny for sharing sexual messages with others, including interns. Despite these problematic

potentials, many adults report that sexting is a satisfying alternative to sexual interaction when they are away from their partners.

Blogs. The word blog is derived from the word weblog. A blog is a webpage where an individual or group can share information or ideas with a large group of people via the internet. It is not uncommon for a person to start a blog and then never update it again. Some of the most successful blogs are updated on a regular basis so the followers of the blog can know when to expect new entries. Blogs cover a wide range of topics, including political issues of all kinds. A common feature to blogs is a feedback forum where, after reading an entry, people can interact with both the blog author and others who have commented. Many traditional media outlets have adopted blog-like features online in order to entice readers to continue sticking with their news or entertainment offerings. For example, many newspaper stories end with the opportunity for readers to share their thoughts or comments about a current issue. These news stories— especially when about hot or particularly partisan political issues—can lead to serious debates. Because of the contentious nature many blogs and news outlets find, it is not uncommon for a user to be required to register in order to participate.

Connection sites. Online dating is another form of social media. Users approach online dating sites—some that require paid membership and others that are free of charge—and create a profile that tells who they are and what they seek in a relationship. Some may be skeptical about how honest some are about the information displayed in an online profile, but research shows that people are generally honest. The stigma placed upon online dating sites has continued to diminish as more people continue to use them in order to meet dating partners. In addition to dating, others may use connection sites to find friends or activity partners. For example, the connection site Meet Up allows users to find activist groups, book clubs, or hobby circles. Users enter a profile, and then they can even send messages to meet up group leaders in order to learn more about the activity or see if they would make a good fit for the group.

Social networking sites. Facebook and other social networking sites are almost ubiquitous features in contemporary culture. Even those who choose not to create an online profile and participate will often hear from others information gained from such social platforms. A key distinguishing feature that makes a social networking site is the fellow list of users that one connects with, usually based upon friendship, family, work relationships, or even weak tie relationships. Initially social networking sites were great ways to meet new people, and although that is still a possibility many social networking sites now discourage people from adding connections they do not know. The public nature of information posted to social networking sites often allow a space for social or political viewpoints to be displayed, although research suggests much of this political activity reinforces pre-existing beliefs – especially because people tend to be online friends with those that are most like them.

2.1.2 The concept of Wifi

WiFi stands for Wireless Fidelity. This term was coined by a branding company, and it only caught on in its abbreviated form. It describes a technology for radio wireless local area networking of devices based on the IEEE 802.11 standards, which are maintained by the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) LAN/MAN Standards Committee (IEEE 802).

The first version of the IEEE 802.11 standards was released in 1997, but their origin dates to 1985 and the release of the ISM band for unlicensed use by the U.S. Federal Communications Commission. Today, multiple revisions of the IEEE 802.11 standards are in use, which is possible thanks to the backward compatibility of IEEE 802.11 hardware.

Similar to the traditional transistor radio, WiFi networks transmit information over the air using radio waves, which are a type of electromagnetic radiation with wavelengths in the electromagnetic spectrum longer than infrared light.

WiFi radio waves typically have the frequency of either 2.4 gigahertz or 5.8 gigahertz. These two WiFi frequency bands are then subdivided into multiple channels, with each channel possibly being shared by many different networks.

When you download a file over a WiFi network, a device known as a wireless router first receives the data from the internet via your broadband internet connection and then converts it into radio waves. The wireless router then emits the radio waves to the surrounding area, and the wireless device that has initiated the download request captures them and decodes them.

Because WiFi depends on radio waves, WiFi networks can be disrupted by interference caused by other WiFi networks or various electronic appliances, including microwave ovens, cordless telephones, refrigerators, televisions, transistor radios, or Bluetooth devices.

To ensure optimal WiFi performance, network administrators often rely on WiFi analyzers such as NetSpot to visualize, manage, and troubleshoot WiFi connections. NetSpot can generate a comprehensive visual map of WiFi networks, highlight areas of signal weakness, and reveal potential causes of interference. In the current era of omnipresent WiFi networks, a tool like NetSpot is indispensable even when setting up a basic WiFi home network.

Most Important WiFi Terminology

Now that we've explained what WiFi stands for and provided you with a widely accepted WiFi definition, it's time to take a closer look at some of the most important WiFi terminology. As you can probably imagine, we can only scratch the surface of the IEEE 802.11 standard here, but knowing the terms described below should be enough to help you make wise purchasing decisions when buying a new WiFi router or selecting a new internet provider.

Wi-Fi Radio Spectrum

802.11 Networking Standards

WiFi Security Protocols

Wi-Fi Radio Spectrum

As we've already mentioned, WiFi is transmitted at the 2.4 GHz and 5 GHz frequencies. In North America, the 2.4 GHz band is divided into 11 channels, with channels 1, 6, and 11 being non-overlapping. The 5 GHz band is divided into a much larger number of channels, with each country applying its own regulations to the allowable channels.

The biggest difference between the two frequency bands is the fact that the 5 GHz signal is only about half the range of the 2.4 GHz signal. What's worse, it has more trouble penetrating walls and solid objects. On the other hand, the 5 GHz band is far less crowded than the 2.4 GHz band, which is a huge advantage in heavily populated urban areas where WiFi networks are virtually everywhere.

802.11 Networking Standards

Most modern WiFi routers support the 802.11ac networking standard, which has a multi-station throughput of at least 1 gigabit per second and single-link throughput of at least 500 megabits per second (500 Mbit/s).

Many older WiFi routers only support the 802.11n networking standard, which has a maximum net data rate of 600 Mbit/s, and some even only support the 802.11g networking standard, which has a maximum net data rate of just 54 Mbit/s.

Since 802.11 networking standards are backward compatible, there's no reason not to purchase a router that supports the latest 802.11n networking standard, which is 802.11ac.

WiFi Security Protocols

WiFi security protocols prevent unauthorized access or damage to computers using wireless networks. The most basic wireless security is Wired Equivalent Privacy (WEP). It was ratified in 1997 and declared deprecated in 2004 because of its security limitations.

WEP was superseded by Wi-Fi Protected Access (WPA) and Wi-Fi Protected Access II (WPA2), which became available in 2003 and 2004 respectively. Soon, WPA2 will be superseded by WPA3, which uses even stronger encryption and mitigates security issues posed by weak passwords.

2.1.3 The concept of mobile phone

Mobile phone data, like GPS data, is passively collected. However, mobile phone datasets have distinct characteristics compared to GPS datasets. Mobile phone data contains location information at much coarser temporal resolution than GPS data. As reviewed by Chen, Ma, Susilo, Liu, and Wang (2016), there are two types of mobile phone data: call detail record (CDR) data and sightings data. These two data types differ in temporal resolution, spatial resolution, and user interactions. Sightings data has higher temporal and spatial resolutions but is not based on user interactions as the case for CDR data. Due to its relatively low temporal and spatial resolutions, the most intuitive application of mobile phone data is to infer trip rates and OD pairs in studying mobility patterns. However, recent advances have demonstrated inferred travel times (Toole et al., 2015) and modes (Wang, He, & Leung, 2018).

Mobile phones have played an important role in people's lives. They have not only been used as a communication device but also served as a sensing device to collect information from its users (Lane et al., 2010). Mainly types of user information: (1) mobile phone usage, and (2)

spatiotemporal traces. In this subsection, we discuss the mobile phone technologies that enable the generation of spatiotemporal traces of users. There are mainly four location systems that can record mobile phone users' spatiotemporal traces: (1) cellular-network-based positioning system (Demissie et al., 2013), (2) GPS positioning system (Wolf et al., 2004), (3) Wi-Fi positioning system (Danalet et al., 2016), and (4) Bluetooth positioning system (Delafontaine et al., 2012). In this chapter, we limit our scope to cellular-network-based positioning system, which generates the most widely applied type of mobile phone data in travel behavior research (Wang et al., 2017).

Mobile phones are able to communicate with each other and connect to the mobile internet, based on cellular networks composed of transceivers that cover their respective land areas. With the movement of a mobile phone, it searches and connects to the nearest transceiver. This process is known as mobile phone positioning (Chen et al., 2016). Positioning data about such connections between users and transceivers are recorded mostly for cellular network operators' own purposes (e.g., billing), which are often not related to transportation, whilst as a by-product, they have been utilized by urban decision makers and researchers to estimate and understand mobility patterns (Wang and Chen, 2018). Because such data are in terms of spatiotemporal traces, researchers named them as mobile phone traces (Jiang et al., 2013a).

Mobile phone traces can be categorized into event-driven traces and network-driven traces (Pinelli et al., 2015). Call detail records and records of internet connections belong to the former one since the production of these data is triggered by user events, including usage of calls, SMS, and internet (Pinelli et al., 2015). Network-driven data are generated regardless whether people are using phones, but either in a periodic way or when a phone moves between two areas. Due to the nature of event-driven traces, their sampling is usually infrequent and could be biased to specific locations, e.g., home locations, and times, e.g.,

during the evenings; on the other hand, the sampling rate of network-driven traces is relatively higher and stable over time (Calabrese et al., 2014).

Spatial inaccuracy has always been an issue if mobile phone traces are used to estimate locations and represent individual mobility (Ahas et al., 2007). There are mainly two causes: (1) the difference between the actual location of a user and the location of the transceiver that the user is connecting to, and (2) the possibility of a user switching the connection between towers due to signal jumps even if the user is not moving (Alexander et al., 2015; Wang and Chen, 2018). To solve the first problem, the simplest way is to regard the transceiver's location or its Voronoi cell as a proxy for the user's location (Montjoye and Smoreda, 2014). Some telecom providers can estimate locations with a higher accuracy based on triangulation with several factors including the number of surrounding cells and received signal strength. The accuracy can reach about 100–500 m in urban areas and 400–10,000 m in rural areas, reported in a Chinese study (Wang et al., 2017b). Qi et al. (2016) named the second problem as the oscillation problem, to which Wang and Chen (2018) have presented an in-depth review on the solutions, including heuristic rules, spatiotemporal clustering, etc. Those algorithms can be used to pre-process mobile phone traces before conducting activity-travel behaviour analysis.

3.0 Methodology

Survey research was adopted for this study. The total population for this study comprised of 50 bank customers and 70 telecommunication users across the three major networks in Nigeria. The data collected for this study was analysed using simple percentage frequency counts and analysis of variance. The composition of the sample size is presented in the table below.

The area of coverage of the research is Imo state capturing bank customers and telecommunication users within the state were generated questionnaires distributed accordingly. The population for the study captures the under listed departments

S/N	Population of the study
Bank Customers	85
Telecom Customers	97
Total	182

Source: Field Survey, 2021

From the population of the study, the sample size is determined using Taro Yamen formula below;

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n = sample size

N = population size

1 = constant figure

e = marginal error of 0.05 or 5%

$$\begin{aligned}
 n &= 182 \\
 &= \frac{182}{1 + 182(0.05)^2} \\
 &= \frac{182}{1 + 182(0.0025)} \\
 &= \frac{182}{1.456} \\
 &= 125
 \end{aligned}$$

3.1 Description of Analytical tool

In the tool's analysis of the research, information will first be edited in order to ascertain their completeness and consistency, the data are then classified and tabulated which later will be followed by the analysis and interpretation of data.

However, only relevant and important questions were considered and analyzed. The analysis of variance statistical techniques will be used for a meaningful, reliable and easy inference.

According to Egbulonu and Nwachukwu (2000) to test the hypothesis regarding equality of population means, we will use the sum of squares of the three types of variance namely;

1. Total Sum of Square (TSS)
2. Treatment Sum of Square (TRSS)
3. Error Sum of Square (ESS)

Where $TSS = TRSS + ESS$

Decision rule

We then look at the f-table for the critical value of the test, with r-1 and n-r degrees of freedom in the table, r-1 is for the numerator and n-e for the denominator degrees of freedom.

The f-distribution.

The null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative accepted is our calculated F value is greater than value found from the table. Otherwise, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The ANOVA calculation performed above

Source of variation	SS	DF	MS	F-Value
Between samples (treatment)	TRSS	r-1	$\frac{TRSS}{r-1}$	$\frac{TRMS}{EMS}$
Within samples (error)	ESS	n-r	$\frac{ESS}{n-1}$	
Total	TSS	n-1		

4.1 Data analysis and interpretation of result

Presentation of data: on the effect of Wifi in digital literacy in Nigeria

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
SA	39	31.2	31.2	31.2
A	40	32.0	32.0	63.2
Valid DA	24	19.2	19.2	82.4
SDA	22	17.6	17.6	100.0
Total	125	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS result output, 2021

The above table shows that 39 representing 31.2% of the respondent are the view that have sufficient knowledge on the usage of wifi, 40 representing 32.2 support the view while 24, 22 of the respondent representing 19.2 and 17.6 respectively are of the opinion that they do not have sufficient knowledge of the use of Wifi.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
WHAT IS THE EFFECT OF WIFI IN DIGITAL LITERACY IN NIGERIA	125	1.00	4.00	2.2320	1.07865
Valid N (listwise)	125				

Source: SPSS result output, 2021

The mean value and its corresponding standard deviation for the above responds was obtained as 2.2320 and 1.07865 respectively. The mean value cut across the average agreement level of the respondent, indicating that majority of the respondent have sufficient knowledge of the use of Wifi.

Presentation of data: on the effect of MOBILE PHONE on DIGITAL LITERACY

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
SA	51	40.8	40.8	40.8
A	23	18.4	18.4	59.2
Valid DA	26	20.8	20.8	80.0
SDA	25	20.0	20.0	100.0
Total	125	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS result output, 2021

The table reveals that 51 representing 40.8% of the respondent strongly agree that ICT parks (mobile phone) influence digital literacy in Nigeria, 23 representing 18.4 support the view while 26, 25 of the respondent representing 20.8% and 20% respectively disagree and strongly disagree on the opinion that ICT parks (mobile phone) influence digital literacy in Nigeria.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
WHAT EFFECT HAS MOBILE PHONE AND DIGITAL LITERACY	125	1.00	4.00	2.2000	1.17775
Valid N (listwise)	125				

Source: SPSS result output, 2021

The mean value and its corresponding standard deviation for the above responds was obtained as 2.2000 and 1.17775 respectively. The mean value cut across the average agreement level of the respondent, indicating that majority of the respondent agree that ICT parks (mobile phone) influence digital literacy in Nigeria.

Presentation of data: on the EXTENT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON DIGITAL LITERACY

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
SA	43	34.4	34.4	34.4
A	43	34.4	34.4	68.8
Valid DA	8	6.4	6.4	75.2
SDA	31	24.8	24.8	100.0
Total	125	100.0	100.0	

Source: SPSS result output, 2021

The table reveals that 43 representing 34.4% of the respondent strongly agree that social media affect digital literacy in Nigeria, 43 representing 34.4 support the view while 8, 31 of the respondent representing 6.4% and 24.8% respectively disagree and strongly disagreed that social media influence digital literacy in Nigeria.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
TO WHAT EXTENT HAS SOCIAL MEDIA AFFECTED DIGITAL LITERACY	125	1.00	4.00	2.2160	1.16801
Valid N (listwise)	125				

Source: SPSS result output, 2021

The mean value and its corresponding standard deviation for the above responds was obtained as 2.2160 and 1.16801 respectively. The mean value cut across the average agreement level of the respondent, indicating that majority of the respondent agrees that ICT parks (social media)influence digital literacy in Nigeria.

Test of hypotheses at 5% level of significance

Presentation of analysis of variance result for hypothesis one.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	20.671	4	5.168	5.017	.001
Within Groups	123.601	120	1.030		
Total	144.272	124			

Source: SPSS result output, 2021

Hypothesis one

H₀₁: Wi-Fi has no significant effect on digital literacy in Nigeria.

From the above result, the estimated f-calculated and its corresponding P-value was obtained as 5.017 and 0.001 respectively. We therefore reject the null hypothesis that WiFi has no significant effect on digital literacy in Nigeria and accept the alternative inferring that the knowledge of respondent of WiFi has significant influence on digital literacy in Nigeria

Presentation of analysis of variance result for hypothesis two.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	10.902	4	2.725	2.030	.044
Within Groups	161.098	120	1.342		
Total	172.000	124			

Source: SPSS result output, 2021

Hypothesis two

H₀₂: Mobile phone has no significant effect on digital literacy in Nigeria.

From the above result, the estimated f-calculated and its corresponding P-value was obtained as 2.030 and 0.044 respectively. We therefore reject the null hypothesis that mobile phone has no significant effect on digital literacy in Nigeria and accept the alternative inferring that the knowledge of respondent of mobile phone has significant influence on digital literacy in Nigeria.

Presentation of analysis of variance result for hypothesis three.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	27.570	4	6.892	5.841	.000
Within Groups	141.598	120	1.180		
Total	169.168	124			

Source: SPSS result output, 2021

Hypothesis three

H₀₃: Social media has no significant effect on digital literacy in Nigeria.

From the above result, the estimated f-calculated and its corresponding P-value was obtained as 5.841 and 0.000 respectively. We therefore reject the null hypothesis that social media has no significant effect on digital literacy in Nigeria and accept the alternative inferring that the knowledge of respondent of social media has significant influence on digital literacy in Nigeria.

Discussion of findings

Having empirically investigated on ICT parks and digital literacy in Nigeria, the study came up with the following findings;

The study revealed, the estimated f-calculated and its corresponding P-value was obtained as 5.017 and 0.001 respectively which is less than 5% level of significance. The study therefore concludes that the knowledge of respondent of WiFi has significant influence on digital literacy in Nigeria.

The study show in the second hypothesis, an estimated f-calculated and its corresponding P-value of 2.030 and 0.044 respectively. This implies we reject the null hypothesis that mobile

phone has no significant effect on digital literacy in Nigeria and accept the alternative inferring that the knowledge of respondent of mobile phone has significant influence on digital literacy in Nigeria.

The third hypothesis revealed an estimated f -calculated and its corresponding P-value of 5.841 and 0.000 respectively which is less than 5% critical level. We therefore reject the null hypothesis that social media has no significant effect on digital literacy in Nigeria and accept the alternative inferring that the knowledge of respondent of social media has significant influence on digital literacy in Nigeria.

The descriptive statistics indicates that a significant percentage of the respondent are of the opinion that the knowledge of the use of WiFi, mobile phone and social media influences digital literacy in Nigeria.

Conclusion

It is imperative that the knowledge of information technology parks has significant impact on digital literacy in Nigeria ICT space as evidence in our study. Developing Nations of the world are gearing towards linking all economic activity to ICT based economy. Like in the case of Nigeria, the ministry of information was changed to ministry of science and digital economy. This implies that all economic and political activities are tied around information communication technological space.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were proffered based on the study

There is need for government to enhance range of coverage of WiFi, since WiFi security protocols prevent unauthorized access or damage to computers using wireless networks.

There is need for mobile phone industry to sensitize their buyer on the various networks assessable on their phone based on the range of coverage.

There is need for constant ICT training on the usage of social media and its economic and social importance in every society.

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